

S2. Full results multivariable multilevel generalized estimated equation models with a gaussian distribution and a identity link function evaluating the association between Bluetongue serotype 3 antibody and vaccination status on milk production between 2020 and 2024 on dairy census data

Variables	Kg milk per cow per day	
	Estimate (95% CI) ¹	P value (Z-test)
Bluetongue serotype 3 & vaccination status		
1. BTV-3 free	Ref.	
2. BTV-3 2023: low BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 ²	-0.34 (-0.45 - -0.23)	<0.0001
3. BTV-3 2023: high BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 ²	-2.14 (-2.32 - -1.96)	<0.0001
4. BTV-3 Inter-Epidemic Period 2024	-0.46 (-0.55 - -0.37)	<0.0001
5. BTV-3 2024: low BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 + unvaccinated	-0.80 (-1.00 - -0.60)	<0.0001
6. BTV-3 2024: low BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 + fully, but not timely vaccinated	+0.30 (0.01 - 0.60)	0.046
7. BTV-3 2024: low BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 + fully and timely vaccinated	-0.21 (-0.61 - 0.20)	0.313
8. BTV-3 2024: low BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 + not fully vaccinated or unknown vaccination status	-0.29 (-0.43 - -0.14)	<0.0001
9. BTV-3 2024: high BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 + unvaccinated	-2.17 (-2.52 - -1.83)	<0.0001
10. BTV-3 2024: high BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 + fully, but not timely vaccinated	-0.48 (-1.08 - 0.12)	0.116
11. BTV-3 2024: high BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 + fully and timely vaccinated	-0.90 (-1.43 - -0.38)	0.001
12. BTV-3 2024: high BTV ab prevalence in April 2024 + not fully vaccinated or unknown vaccination status	-1.67 (-1.89 - -1.44)	<0.0001
13. BTV-3 2024: no BTV ab in April 2024 + unvaccinated	-0.30 (-0.50 - -0.09)	0.006
14. BTV-3 2024: no BTV ab in April 2024 + fully, but not timely vaccinated	+0.83 (0.52 - 1.14)	<0.0001
15. BTV-3 2024: no BTV ab in April 2024 + fully and timely vaccinated	+0.71 (0.16 - 1.26)	0.012
16. BTV-3 2024: no BTV ab in April 2024 + not fully vaccinated or unknown vaccination status	+0.18 (0.04 - 0.31)	0.01
Province		
Average Netherlands (NL)	Ref.	
Groningen-Limburg	Varying	
Season		
Average NL	Ref.	
1st quarter: winter	+0.51 (0.49 - 0.53)	<0.0001
2nd quarter: spring	+0.83 (0.82 - 0.85)	<0.0001
3rd quarter: summer	-0.52 (-0.54 - -0.50)	<0.0001
4th quarter: autumn	-0.82 (-0.84 - -0.80)	<0.0001

Herd size (n cows >2 years)		
Average NL		Ref.
		-3.07
≤10%: smallest (median=38)	(-3.28 - -2.85)	<0.0001
		-0.71
>10 - ≤50%: smaller (median=76)	(-0.83 - -0.59)	<0.0001
		+1.16
>50 - ≤90%: higher (median=130)	(1.04 - 1.27)	<0.0001
		+2.62
>90%: highest (median=250)	(2.45 - 2.80)	<0.0001
Type of milking parlour		
Conventional (55%)		Ref.
		+1.92
Automated (35%)	(1.77 - 2.07)	<0.0001
		-3.11
Unknown (10%)	(-3.39 - -2.83)	<0.0001
Herd health status		
BVDV not free (10%)		Ref.
		+0.66
BVDV free (90%)	(0.53 - 0.80)	<0.0001
BoHV-1 not free (44%)		Ref.
		+1.29
BoHV-1 free (56%)	(1.15 - 1.44)	<0.0001
Paratuberculosis unknown (17%)		Ref.
		+0.40
Paratuberculosis unsuspected (83%)	(0.28 - 0.52)	<0.0001
Salmonellosis bulk milk negative (98.3%)		Ref.
		-0.40
Salmonellosis bulk milk positive (1.7%)	(-0.62 - -0.18)	0.001
Introduction of cattle in the previous year		
Yes (52%)		Ref.
		-0.06
No (48%)	(-0.18 - 0.06)	0.321
		0.0004
		(-0.000-
Trend in time (four weekly level)	0.0007)	0.210
		23.73
Constant	(23.54-23.92)	<0.0001

¹CI=Confidence interval

²Low antibody (ab) prevalence is defined as an estimated antibody prevalence below 50% in the group of lactating cattle based on a single evaluation of antibodies in bulk tank milk in April 2024. High antibody (ab) prevalence is defined as an estimated antibody prevalence of 50% or higher in the group of lactating cattle based on a single evaluation of antibodies in bulk tank milk in April 2024.